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“SUN AND RAIN”

A free shower of tears pours from the weeping sky.
The dry earth absorbs much gratefulness.
But the small seed is overwhelmed by endless sorrow.
And sobbing all day doesn't fill anything.

With a burning kindness, the golden sun ascends, and
lights the world everywhere.
But blinding light can parch.
And the soft happiness of the night is stolen by relentless daylight.

A likely pattern, a balance pursued,
where the sun shines and the rain falls.
The clouds start to part as the storm departs.
The tired heart is revived by a hopeful light.

In life too, the shadows have their place.
So does the radiance of a smiling face.
Let gloom yield and light descend slowly.
Because neither lasts forever.